

Title

Piperidine-based compounds in melanoma preclinical models: a scoping review protocol

Authors

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Population- Concept-Context framework

Population (P): melanoma (cell lines, animal models)

Concept (C): piperidine-based compounds

Context (C): anticancer activity, molecular mechanisms, toxicity

Research question

What is the current evidence regarding the anticancer effect, mechanisms of action, and toxicity of piperidine-based compounds in preclinical melanoma models?

Objectives of the review

The objectives of this review are:

- to identify studies investigating piperidine-based compounds in melanoma preclinical models;
- to classify piperidine-based compounds on chemical structure and antimelanoma mechanism;
- to summarize reported anticancer effects (e.g., cytotoxicity, apoptosis, metastasis inhibition, angiogenesis inhibition,...);
- to describe the identified molecular mechanisms of action;
- to identify gaps in current research and potential directions for future studies.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria:

1. original research articles (*in vitro*, *in vivo*);
2. studies involving melanoma cell lines (e.g., A375, SK-MEL-28,...) and melanoma animal models;
3. studies evaluating piperidine-based compounds;
4. articles reporting anticancer activity or molecular mechanism data;

Exclusion criteria:

1. secondary studies: review articles, meta-analyses, editorials;
2. non-melanoma studies;
3. non-piperidine compounds;
4. clinical studies involving human subjects

5. only *in silico* evaluation
6. no full-text available

Data sources

1. PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>)
2. Scopus (<https://www.scopus.com/>)
3. Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com/>)

Search strategy

Search terms: piperidine, melanoma, A375, SK-MEL, B16F10

Search sequences and filters

1. PubMed

Search string: (piperidine[Title/Abstract] OR "piperidine derivatives"[Title/Abstract]) AND (melanoma[Title/Abstract] OR "melanoma cells"[Title/Abstract] OR A375[Title/Abstract] OR B16F10[Title/Abstract] OR SK-MEL[Title/Abstract])

Filters: Search field (title/abstract), Article language (English), Publication date: none (no restriction)

2. WOS

Search string: TS = (piperidine OR "piperidine derivatives") AND TS=(melanoma OR "melanoma cells" OR A375 OR B16F10 OR SK-MEL)

Filters: Search field (topic), Document type (Article); Language (English), Date range: none (no restriction)

3. Scopus

Search string: TITLE-ABS-KEY (piperidine OR "piperidine derivatives") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (melanoma OR "melanoma cells" OR A375 OR B16F10 OR SK-MEL)

Filters: Search within (article title, abstract and keywords); Document type (limited to Article), Language (limited to English), Year range: none (no restriction)

Study selection process

All records retrieved from databases will be exported in .csv format and further refined in a two-phase screening process.

1. Initial screening: The titles and abstracts of retrieved articles will be independently reviewed by two reviewers according to the previously defined inclusion and exclusion criteria.
2. Secondary screening: The full-text articles will be independently assessed by two reviewers according to the previously defined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Any disagreements will be resolved through discussion within the research group and the selection process results will be presented using a PRISMA flow diagram.

Data extraction

A standardized form (Google Sheets) will be used for data extraction.

Extracted variables will include:

1. Study characteristics: first author name, year of publication and country;

2. Experimental model: study type (*in vitro*, *in vivo*), melanoma model used (cell line, animal model), piperidine derivative (2D structure, classification according to type of substituents: aliphatic, aromatic);
3. Outcomes measured: reported biological activity (IC₅₀, viability, etc.), toxicity (in animal models), and molecular mechanism involved.

Data analysis and synthesis

Results will be presented as a narrative synthesis based on thematic grouping (*in vitro* results, *in vivo* results, molecular mechanisms, chemical classes, toxicity reported) and will include representative tables. Due to the expected heterogeneity of studies, no meta-analysis will be performed.

Quality assessment

The following methodological characteristics of the included studies will be described: study type (*in vitro*, *in vivo*), experimental model (cell lines or animal models), piperidine derivatives investigated and biological outcomes measured. No risk of bias assessment is planned for the review.

Reporting guidelines

This review will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews guidelines.

Dissemination

Findings of this review are intended for inclusion in a bachelor's thesis and a peer-reviewed article.

Registration details

This protocol was registered on the Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org/>) before data extraction and can be accessed at: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1967662.